

IRISCC

D6.6

Recommendations for data policy and procedures for digital service provision

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Abstract

Key words

Data Policy, Recommendations, Digital service provision, RIs

This report provides recommendations for data policy and procedures for effective provision of existing and newly developed digital services by the RIs participating in the IRISCC landscape. It supports the development of a uniform data policy to fit the specificity of the integrated cross-RI services developed for climate change research and to serve as the base for defining requirements for the access management system to be customised and operated in IRISCC's WP8.

The report includes an overview of the existing data policies and procedures for digital service provision established and used by participating RIs, building from, and expanding the work carried out in previous EC-funded projects (ENVRIplus, ATMO-ACCESS) to analyse and identify their best practices. This work also benefits from the experience gained in the development of the policy framework and access to the data and services to be provided by the future Distributed System of Scientific Collections Research Infrastructure.

The resulting best practices are composed into concrete recommendations to harmonise the current data policies and access practices of RIs participating in IRISCC, including Open Science, FAIR principles, ethics, and legal framework, to optimally provide digital services via IRISCC and organise the management of the infrastructure. The document concludes with guidelines for the way forward and implementation of the recommendations, and a model of data and service provision policy for IRISCC.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure. Service that enables members of different institutions to access protected information that is distributed on different web servers.
API	Application Programming Interface. Set of rules or protocols that enables software applications to communicate with each other to exchange data, features and functionality.
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections. New world-class RI for digitisation and access to natural science collections.
DMP	Data Management Plan. Document specifying how research data will be handled both during and after a research project.
DOIs	Digital Object Identifiers. Type of unique, persistent identifier (PID) specifically for digital objects.
EC	European Commission. The main executive body of the European Union.
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud. Multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services, enabling them to better conduct their work.
ERA	European Research Area. Single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU.
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium. Specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructure.
ESA	European Space Agency. European agency for space exploitation.
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures. Strategic instrument to develop the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach.
EU	European Union. Supranational political and economic union of 27 member states that are located primarily in Europe.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Four foundational principles that serve to guide data producers and publishers in making data FAIR.

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation. The EU GDPR governs how the personal data of individuals in the EU may be processed and transferred.
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights. Rights given to persons over the creations of their minds.
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks. Project providing scientific and knowledge services to foster cutting-edge research and evidence-based policymaking to improve Europe's resilience to climate change.
IT	Information Technology. Theory and practice of using computers to store and analyse information.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator. Key quantifiable indicators of progress toward an intended result.
MS	Milestone. Significant step in project development.
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PIDs	Persistent identifiers. Long-lasting reference to a document, file, web page, or other object.
Remote Access	Access to resources and way for users to engage with data, services and digital tools without the need for physical presence.
RI	Research Infrastructure. Facilities, resources and services used by the science community to conduct research and foster innovation.
SLAs	Service Level Agreements. Agreement defining the level of service expected by a customer from a supplier.
TA	Transnational Access. Access provision, often free-of-charge, to resources and services from research infrastructures to selected users or user groups working in countries other than the one where the infrastructure is located.
VA	Virtual Access. Access to Users provided through communication networks, such as Access to data and digital tools.
VRE	Virtual Research Environments. Online system helping researchers to collaborate.

WP	Work Package. Defined subtask within a project to achieve a specific goal or result.
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Executive summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive set of recommendations to harmonise data policies and procedures for digital service provision within the IRISCC (Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks) network. It supports the development of a coherent and interoperable policy environment across the participating Research Infrastructures (RIs), to enhance user access and improve the sustainability and impact of services addressing climate change risks.

The recommendations are based on a thorough review of current data policies and digital service practices in key RIs involved in IRISCC, as well as lessons learned from previous European projects such as ENVRI-FAIR and ATMO-ACCESS. The report further integrates recent experience gained regarding RIs, from the development of the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo), particularly regarding policy framework design and access strategies.

Key recommendations focus on aligning with Open Science and FAIR data principles, while ensuring legal compliance (e.g., GDPR, IPR, licences), ethical standards, and robust metadata and documentation practices. The document provides guidance on access procedures, licencing frameworks, user support, and service interoperability, with a view to streamlining and federating service delivery across disciplines and infrastructures.

A model policy template is included to facilitate adoption of the recommendations by IRISCC partners. The overall goal is to ensure that data and digital services provided via IRISCC are accessible, reliable, and effectively governed, thus enabling high-impact climate research and informed policymaking.

The proposed policy framework will provide a strong foundation for the access management system under development in IRISCC Work Package 8 (WP8).

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The overall objective of the Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks (IRISCC) WP6 is to harmonise transnational and virtual access policies and procedures for efficient access management and provision, as well as to enable a positive user experience in accessing installations and digital services, and to deploy and provide a technical interoperability framework for integrated IRISCC services.

Task 6.2 is aimed at harmonising the current access practices of Research Infrastructures (RIs, [R1 & R2]), by adapting similar access policies, including ethics and equal opportunity aspects, will help to optimally provide services and organise the IRISCC Transnational Access (TA) management.

This Deliverable 6.6 gives recommendations for data policy and procedures for provision of digital services. It builds on previous European Commission-funded projects (ENVRI-FAIR, ATMO-ACCESS), to provide an overview of the existing data policies and best practices from RIs participating in IRISCC regarding provision of their digital services. It also benefits from the experience gained in the development of the policy framework and access to the data and services in the framework of the future Distributed System of Scientific Collections (**DiSSCo**) RI.

Policies and provision of services of existing RIs have been analysed to assess their best practices, highlighting common trends and differences that could be harmonised. The best practices have then been reformulated into recommendations to fit the specificity of the integrated cross-RI services developed for climate change research within IRISCC. The recommendations are designed to serve as a basis for defining an optimal user experience in accessing and using the data and services provided via IRISCC. The objective is to design harmonised data policy and procedures for effective provision of existing and newly developed digital services to be provided by the RIs in the IRISCC landscape. The document thus also provides guidelines for the way forward and implementation of the recommendations, and a model of data and service provision policy for IRISCC (Annex 2). This work overall ensures that the access management system follows standardised procedure for the provision of services and maximises the sustainability of IRISCC beyond the project.

1.2 Methodology

The main phases of the methodological approach adopted are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methodological approach

The work builds on the experience of previous EC-funded projects and infrastructures (ATMO-ACCESS, ENVRI-FAIR) in developing data policies for the provision of digital services. A desk analysis of the state of the art of the existing data policies and modalities was carried out, adopted for service provision by the infrastructures involved in IRISCC. The analysis focused on the infrastructures that are already mature enough to provide governance documents and established services. The information collected were organised in tables to obtain a landscape of the best practices and differences regarding their data policies and the main characteristics of provision of digital services across the IRISCC RIs.

Information gathered from existing RIs was benchmarked against the work done at RBINS for DiSSCo, which is a pan-European distributed RI aiming at digitising and unifying virtual and physical accesses to European natural science collections. Currently in its transition phase to becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), DiSSCo is developing key policies to support its operations. The Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences is leading the development of the Policy Framework, including the Data and Access Policies, to ensure interoperability and sustainability. This expertise provides an asset for benchmarking and designing recommendations for Data Policy and service provision within IRISCC. The experience gained through DiSSCo's policy development offers a strong foundation for harmonising data governance across research infrastructures.

The results of the analysis of best practices and differences across the IRISCC RIs, combined with results from former work and the experience gained from DiSSCo allowed us to formulate concrete recommendations to harmonise data policies and practices and to guide the development of a data policy and procedure for service provision for IRISCC.

2 Background

2.1 European Research Infrastructures and digital services

2.1.1 Research Infrastructure and Research Infrastructure's landscape

RIs provide key research facilities and research services supporting the advancement of knowledge and innovation in Europe. These can include large-scale research equipment, data repositories, computing systems, and communication networks. RIs can be physically centralised, distributed across locations, or entirely virtual under the form of digital platforms. The European Union, through programs such as Horizon Europe and initiatives like the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI, [R1]), emphasises the importance of RIs in supporting cross-border collaboration and transnational access to facilities, promoting technological advancements, and addressing societal challenges. By supporting their development and sustainability, the EU strengthens the European Research Area (ERA).

A critical aspect of RIs is their data policies. These policies could entail that research data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), support open science and maximise the impact of research activities. Data policies can define how data sharing is facilitated, how sensitive information is protected, how long-term preservation is ensured, and how the reproducibility of scientific findings is supported.

RIs can provide a variety of essential services to researchers, including access to datasets and cutting-edge equipment, repositories and data management tools, and training programs. Those services are usually supplied by Service Providers (sometimes called service/central facilities), i.e. an organisation or institution member of the RI that offers one or more services through an agreement with the RI. Service Provider Agreements are often used to define the exact nature of each service that outline the responsibilities of Service Providers and ensure the delivery of high-quality services in alignment with the overall objectives of the RI. By integrating resources and services, RIs thus enhance innovation and contribute significantly to addressing global challenges.

RIs are an integral component of Europe's research and innovation ecosystem. By promoting collaboration and open science, and providing essential services, they contribute significantly to addressing societal challenges and achieving European research priorities.

2.1.2 RIs and Digital Services within IRISCC

IRISCC involves key European RIs (Figure 2) that bring together diverse expertise to address climate change risks.

Figure 2. IRISCC project dashboard highlighting the landscape of RIs participating in IRISCC (Source: IRISCC Grant Agreement)

The RIs participating in IRISCC are listed in Table 1. The list has been obtained by gathering the RI's that are partners of IRISCC or represented by one or more of their members. These RIs provide essential services across natural and social sciences, contributing to improved resilience and informed policy decisions.

The resources to be provided via IRISCC will deliver a range of services to support research and policymaking for climate adaptation. The adopted approach for IRISCC is to provide services by integrating existing RIs, develop new services, and harmonise access management systems. This method will ensure a comprehensive, cross-disciplinary service portfolio tailored to climate change risk research and innovation.

The services to be provided by IRISCC shall include integrated societally relevant knowledge services, with a focus on environmental, climatology, soils study, atmospheric, health, water and carbon cycles, and chemical aspects. Services around the management, curation, and sharing of environmental data will be fundamental. Risk assessment tools, such as drought and heatwaves services, and service for marine ecosystems biodiversity, will enable users to model hazards and vulnerabilities while forecasting climate risks. The development of user-centric Service Design Labs will facilitate co-creation between researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders, fostering tailored solutions. Virtual and remote access will be supported through a dedicated online catalogue and access management system to digital services.

The project will establish a catalogue of services that will connect existing services provided by individual RIs, allowing users to access thematically catalogued data and tools for studying individual risk determinants. The catalogue will also integrate cross-RI services and customised offerings to provide tailored data products to address multi-hazard risks and facilitate thematic access calls. Eventually, new services will be collaboratively co-created for the *Knowledge Services* through a transdisciplinary process involving stakeholders and operational service providers. Services and external data will be accessible to users via the gateway provided by IRISCC.

By offering a structured and coordinated entry point to data and services, IRISCC aims to maximise accessibility and utility across different user communities. Access to these services will be managed via a federated and centralised access management system, building upon existing RI-specific systems, thus showing a need for harmonisation of data policies and procedures for digital services provision across the RIs participating in IRISCC.

Table 1 - List of RIs participating in IRISCC

RIs participating in IRISCC				
Acronym	Full name	Website	Webpage for Governance Documents (Data Policy)	Access to data and digital services
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure	https://www.actris.eu/	ACTRIS ERIC documents ACTRIS	ACTRIS Data Portal
AnaEE ERIC	Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems	https://www.anaee.eu/	Governance, Strategy & Development Plans AnaEE-ERIC	Data and models portals AnaEE-ERIC
D4Science	Data for Science	https://www.d4science.org/	-	Services D4Science
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	https://www.ecmwf.int/	Official documents ECMWF	Access to forecasts ECMWF
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure	https://www.egi.eu/	Publications - EGI	https://www.egi.eu/services/

EIRENE RI	Research Infrastructure for Environmental Exposure assessment in Europe	https://eirene.eu/	–	–
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research	https://elter-ri.eu/	–	eLTER - Service Portal (coming soon)
EMBRC	European Marine Biology Resource Center	https://www.embrc.eu/	Governance EMBRC	Access to services
Gesis	Gesellschaft Sozialwissenschaftlicher Infrastruktureinrichtungen	https://www.gesis.org/en/home	–	https://www.gesis.org/en/services
IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System	https://www.iagos.org/	Data Policy – IAGOS	IAGOS Data & Services: https://iagos.aeris-data.fr/ ATMO ACCESS (VA): https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/#/
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System	https://www.icos-cp.eu/	Reports and documents ICOS	https://www.icos-cp.eu/dataANDservices
Is-enes	Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling	https://is.enes.org/	–	Models & tools: https://is.enes.org/services-models-tools/ Data & Metadata: https://is.enes.org/services-data-metadata/
OPTED	Observatory for Political Texts in European Democracies	https://opted.eu/	–	–

SeaDataNet	Pan-European infrastructure for ocean & marine data management	https://www.seadatanet.org/	Data policy - SeaDataNet & Technical documentation - SeaDataNet	https://www.seadatanet.org/Data-Access
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2.2 Overview of Data Policies and procedures for digital service provision

2.2.1 Best practices regarding Data Policies from RIs participating in IRISCC

This section provides an overview of the current data policies in the IRISCC RIs through the characterisation of the following indicators: audience and scope of the policies, access principles, licencing, data quality management, intellectual property, acknowledgment requirements, data embargo, legal compliance, monitoring and reporting, commercial use and user support.

The results are shown in Table 2, which accommodates these indicators in the rows and the RIs in the columns.

Table 2 – Overview of Data Policies from RIs participating in IRISCC

Overview of Data Policies from RIs participating in IRISCC											
RIs Topics	ACTRIS	ANAE	D4Science	ECMWF	EGI	eLTER	EMBRC	GESIS	IAGOS	ICOS	SeaDataNet
Audience	<u>ACTRIS Data Policy</u> Users, public and private, European and non-European. Data policies included in <u>Rules of Operations</u> and in <u>Procedure to access the resources</u>	No governance document found	<u>Conditions for Access</u> addressed to licensees agreeing on the terms and conditions of the policy, educational and research institutions, using meteorological data for non-commercial purposes	No governance document found	No governance document available yet	Data policy and DMP in <u>Rules of Operations</u> , covering users accessing marine research infrastructure, including researchers and commercial users under specific agreements	No governance document found	<u>Data Policy</u> for researchers and climate scientists accessing IAGOS' atmospheric and climate-related data	<u>Data Policy</u> for scientists, policymakers, research institutions, agencies, and the public using environmental data	<u>Data Policy</u> for researchers, governmental agencies, and environmental stakeholders	
Scope	Data and digital tools generated by National Facilities and Topical Centres for	Data generated by research, monitoring, and surveys involving	–	Meteorological data and products	–	–	Data generated through surveys, research, and monitoring activities	–	Data on atmospheric composition and climate	Greenhouse gases measurement data and related products for climate research	Marine and oceanographic data from participating organisations

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	atmospheric research	AnaEE platforms									
Access Principles	Open access with FAIR principles	Open access and FAIR principles for research based on scientific excellence, platform feasibility, and resource availability	Promotion of open access principles, data sharing and interoperability aligned with FAIRness.	Promotes open access	–	Open data policies under FAIR principles. Aims to make data from long-term ecosystem research available to the public	Open access, implementing FAIR principles, with conditions defined by the DMP	Data is openly accessible but downloading requires registration.	Promotes the wide availability of data with open access principles and possibilities to share and adapt the data at will	Open and FAIR access; Login permits to permanently agree to licences and conditions of use, otherwise agreement is required for each download	Open access to most data under a Creative Commons license; restricted access for sensitive datasets
Licensing	Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) for data and metadata	Open access, with potential grace periods for exclusive user access	All derivative products made publicly available are licenced under the CC BY 4.0 except where	Non-commercial licences; research activities must ensure open results. Licence	Use of open standards and licences	Creative Commons copyright licences when using third-party materials	Data should be licenced under the most recent version of Creative Commons CC-BY	–	IAGOS data is licenced under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0)	ICOS data is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0)	CC-BY 4.0 for open-access data

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			noted otherwise								
Data Quality Management	Data quality control with National Facilities responsible for data submission	Data producers are responsible for maintaining secure and accurate records of the data	–	–	–	–	Embargo periods defined for quality control and exclusive research	–	Data processing levels with various quality controls	Quality control and data processing by ICOS Central Facilities	Quality controlled by data providers following best practices.
Intellectual Property (IP)	Originators retain rights; ACTRIS ERIC gets perpetual non-exclusive usage rights	All IP rights created, arising from, obtained or developed by AnaEE-ERIC during its activities shall be owned by AnaEE-ERIC	–	IP retained by ECMWF; no transfer of ownership	Agreements for intellectual property and confidentiality	–	Data creators retain rights; IP exceptions for sensitive data	–	Rights remain with originators	National Networks and Central Facilities retain ownership; ICOS ERIC gets perpetual rights	Data originators retain IP rights
Acknowledgment Requirements	Citation and attribution to data originators mandatory. Attribution given to	Usage and publication tracking required	Instructions for different cases (VRE, Services, etc.)	Publications must acknowledge ECMWF following good	–	Clear rules with ready sentence to copy and paste	“Outcomes resulting from work carried out using EMBC services must acknowledge	No specific instructions; “Cite” buttons are associated with provided publications	Clear instructions in the Data Policy . IAGOS assigns DOIs to data collections to	PIDs and acknowledgment system . For all data the citation is provided on the landing	Users must acknowledge data sources. Any person making substantial use of data

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	ACTRIS ERIC in case substantial number of metadata is harvested by external metadata services.			scientific practices.			EMBRC-ERIC, the Node(s), etc... "	or datasets, to ease attribution	facilitate acknowledgment	page of the data object.	must communicate with the data source prior to publication and should possibly consider the data source(s) for co-authorship.
Data Embargo	Short-term embargo possible for sensitive data	Possible grace period of 12 months after the data are made available to the user. The user can request a larger grace period but has to document the extent and reasons for it in its application .	-	-	-	-	Allowed for exclusive research. Embargo period shall be defined in the User Access Contract.	-	Embargo guidelines may apply	Available by request for pre-quality control data and data that is part of or supplement to an article under review	No general embargo; restrictions apply to sensitive data.

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Legal Compliance	INSPIRE, Aarhus Convention, OECD Guidelines	Aligned with OECD Guidelines and INSPIRE principles.	–	WMO Resolution 40, EU Database Directive	–	–	EOSC Declaration, OECD Principles	–	Relevant EU and international frameworks	INSPIRE Directive, Aarhus Convention, PSI Directive	Aligned with EU and international data-sharing principles.
Monitoring & Reporting	Data Centre Management Board oversees compliance	Use of KPIs for access and usage monitoring	–	–	–	–	Usage tracked via KPIs	–	Periodic reviews for compliance	Data usage tracked via the data portal	Usage tracked through user agreements.
Commercial Use	Restricted or delayed in specific cases	Governed by specific agreements as outlined in SLA	–	Commercial activities excluded from free access	–	–	Requires separate agreement for commercial use	–	–	Possible charges for commercial use	Requires separate agreements.
User Support	Helpdesk available for technical support to access and use the platform's tools, digital services and the data	Coordinated by the AnaEE-ERIC Central Hub and web portal for applications and administrative processes	Help centre providing detailed documentation for digital services, including user manuals, APIs, and best practices	Support portal	Webpage and contact to request support	For each service, the Service Portal will provide clear documentation, points of contact and training materials	Online contact point to request help or for questions regarding access to data and services.	Online feedback form available on the website, with guidance to travel to the HQ of GESIS	Online contact point for information	Help page and guidance to access the data portal. Detailed documentation for digital services, including user manuals, APIs, and best practices	Assistance provided through user services. Detailed guidance provided on each service webpage

2.2.2 Best practices regarding Data Policies from former assessments

This section reviews a series of documents assessing data and access policies in the RI landscape. These policies reflect established best practices in research data management, covering key areas such as data access, sharing, licensing, and protection of intellectual property. This review aims to inform and strengthen IRISCC's policy framework, ensuring compatibility and harmonisation with broader research ecosystems.

ATMO-ACCESS WPI Milestone 1.2: Analysis of Access policies and legal framework regulating the Access provision

The Milestone report of ATMO-ACCESS [R3] analyses and integrates the legal framework regulating the access, data access and use of services in 19 RIs. It also considers the requirements for common user policy and/or user service agreements to address the scope of rights and responsibilities between facility operators and users for synergistic use of atmospheric facilities.

The report emphasises compliance with FAIR principles and alignment with EU regulations such as the GDPR and the Aarhus Convention. Key recommendations for a data policy include establishing policies on data storage, access, and personal data protection, ensuring metadata standards, and managing IPR through (open access) licensing (e.g., CC BY). For digital service provision, it outlines user eligibility requirements, including peer-reviewed access modes and adherence to national and EU legislation. Additionally, it encourages open access to publications, proper data citation, and user agreements that define rights, responsibilities, and IPR ownership.

FAIR-enabling Data Policy Checklist

The FAIR-enabling Data Policy Checklist [R4] provides recommendations for creating data policies that support FAIR practices. It breaks down policy assessment into three sections: context, content, and support for compliance. Key recommendations for data policy include defining the scope of research outputs, aligning with FAIR principles, requiring DMPs, supporting metadata sharing, and clarifying licensing and IPR. For digital service provision, it advises clear communication on data sharing, repository use, data citation, and preservation timelines. Additionally, it highlights the importance of compliance monitoring, guidance provision, and cost support for FAIR data management practices.

D4.6 ENVRI-FAIR Draft Policy Document for the Common Service Catalogue

The ENVRI-FAIR Deliverable 4.6 [R5] compares policy documents of various RIs and provides recommendations for practical implementation of policies. It emphasises alignment with the EOSC Rules of Participation and the FAIR principles, ensuring all participating RIs provide sustainable, transparent, and interoperable data services. The document defines core policy statements across areas such as data management, PIDs, metadata standards, access protocols, and provenance tracking. It highlights the need for RIs to create clear policies, guidelines, and IT implementations, ensuring compatibility with the [ENVRI-Hub](#) and fostering interoperability within the EOSC ecosystem. Additionally, it stresses the importance of policies on privacy, licensing, terms and conditions, and cookies, identifying these policies as critical for compliance and user protection. The document encourages RIs to leverage best practices and develop common standards to reduce friction in cross-infrastructure operations.

D4.7 ENVRI-FAIR Report on Policies for the Common Service Catalogue

The ENVRI-FAIR Deliverable 4.7 [R6] presents the policies planned for the ENVRI-Hub service catalogue within the context of interoperation with EOSC and the FAIR principles. The report lists key required policies, including those on licensing, authentication, authorisation, metadata (FAIR compliance), provenance, citation, curation, and disaster recovery. It stresses the need for RIs to develop aligned internal policies and guidelines covering data provision, access management, personal data privacy, and security. The document also encourages the use of a policy template for creation of a data policy to ensure consistency and compatibility across RIs policies.

2.2.3 Best practices regarding Services provision from participating RIs

This section provides an overview of services provision within RIs participating in IRISCC through the characterisation of the following indicators: sets of services provided, protocol for virtual access, online service catalogue, registration and affiliation requirements, user profiles, restrictions and agreements for access and service provision, fees, application requirements & review processes.

The results are shown in Table 3, which accommodates these indicators in the rows and the RIs in the columns.

Table 3 – Overview of services provision within RIs participating in IRISCC

Overview of services provision within RIs participating in IRISCC											
RIs Topics	ACTRIS	ANAEE	D4Science	ECMWF	EGI	eLTER	EMBRC	GESIS	IAGOS	ICOS	SeaDataNet
Services provided	Datasets, calibrations, digital services, request measurement services, request for TNA	Datasets, data models, facilities, experimental platforms, analytical services, catalogues of virtual research environments, computational tools, and funding	Data storage, processing tools, and VREs	Datasets, forecast products, and tools for analysis	Advanced computing, storage resource, data space and service hosting	Datasets, analytical tools, physical access to research sites	Datasets and range of on-site and remote services offered by marine stations and institutes in EMBRC's member countries	Support to collect data, access to datasets, analytical and processing tools, data storage and sharing facilities	Datasets (air quality, greenhouse gases, and weather phenomena), visualisation tools, software, derived and elaborated products	Datasets, tools, VREs, data visualisation, software, data processing pipelines, elaborated products, collection processes and community services	Metadata, Data, Software, and Data Products
Protocol for virtual access	Via the ACTRIS data centre	Via single-entry API web portal	Via registration as a user and a request for access	Via Web API portal	Via application process requiring to register or to join the EGI	Via eLTER – Service Portal (Coming soon)	Via application links in the service catalogue and user application through service portal	Via the via the service catalogue and registration. Some services also require application	Via IAGOS portal , also via Virtual Access – ATMO-ACCESS	Via Data Portal	Via Common Data Index service

			Access can be granted to individuals or research groups		Federation.			via a form provided directly on their webpages			
Online Service Catalogue	Yes, https://actris.eu/catalogue-of-services	Yes, https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalogue/1/services	Yes, https://services.d4science.org/catalogue-d4s	Yes, https://www.ecmwf.int/	Yes, https://www.egi.eu/services/	Yes, through data portal: https://portal.eiter.eu/en-gb	Yes, https://www.embrc.eu/service-catalogue	Yes, Research-based services for your survey project	Yes, IAGOS – In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System	Yes, Data and services ICOS	Yes, for each type of service
Login Required	Not for accessing the data, but login required to access some services: Login ACTRIS	Yes, to access research APIs developed by ANAEE and partners: Sign up - AnaEE API	Yes, to access the resources: Sign in to D4Science Accounts prod	Yes, Users need to register and comply with specific conditions to use data and services, including request for access: Log in to ECMWF	Depending on the services to access.	Services both requiring registration or accessible via a visualisation tool: Choose how to log in	No, but access request via “apply” links is requested to access the services and data.	Downloading the data and accessing the services requires to login with GESIS: Login	Yes, to download data and access the services: Log in to AERIS-SSO	No, only to download data while bypassing the ICOS data licence, otherwise acceptance, is needed for every download. Also, some services require registration and login.	Yes, to access data and products, via the Common Data Index service: https://www.marine-id.org/pwm/public/NewUser?

										Login to Carbon Portal	
Affiliation Required	Yes	No, but login possible with institutional account	No. Login possible with various credentials (institutional, Google, LinkedIn, etc)	No	Yes, to a legal entity	Yes, or via Google or ORCID	No	No	No, login possible with ORCID or institution account if it's part of the EduGAIN federation	No, login possible with ORCID, Edugain or social networks ID	Not mandatory.
User profiles	Yes (e.g., academia, policymakers)	Yes (e.g., public sector, industry, academia)	–	Yes. User Profile access: Member State, Commercial customers, ECMWF staff member, researchers, public, satellite data provider	3 groups of users: research, Business, Federation	Yes, (e.g., service provider, researcher...).	No	–	–	–	Yes, business, academia, government or unaffiliated.

Restrictions	Peer-review application for competitive access	Feasibility and scientific review	Registration procedure to access the moderated VREs	Restricted access to specific user groups due to the sensitivity of the data, with different types and conditions of access for the different user groups: https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/accessing-forecasts	Restricted access to sensitive data via registration and application process.	–	Services are provided in the countries members of EMBRC.	–	Data sorted within 4 levels. Levels 0 & 1 are restricted data.	–	SeaDataNet makes data available without restriction, meaning without discrimination against, for example, individuals, research groups, or nationality
Agreement	For temporary data restriction only (See Data Policy)	SLA between AnaEE and National Nodes to deliver the services, to organise and coordinate the services and to organise communications between AnaEE and the National Platforms	Can establish SLA	–	Bilateral partnership available through Memorandum of understanding	–	SLA between EMBRC and legal entities operating as Nodes regulating the provision of services and resources, to cover those services and resources to be dedicated to the EMBRC as provided by the Operators and contained on the EMBRC website."	Some sensitive data require a data use, agreements to ensure privacy and ethical use of the data	Agreement to the licencing conditions that apply to the data	Agreement to the licencing conditions that apply to the data	–

Fees	Possible fees for competitive access	Fees based on platform usage; Defined by SLA between AnaEE and the platform	Free of charge	Free of charge except under justified restrictions (e.g., commercial sensitivity). Pricing system in place to calculate the access and licence fees for accessing services by different types of users.	1) Sponsored access, no cost associated; 2) Sponsored access, no cost associated; and 3) Paid access	Under discussion.	Services are billed based on their nature (scope and number) and duration of use. Access to data is generally free of charge. Some facilities offer on-site accommodation and catering at rates far below market rate (i.e. nearby hotels). All services are billed at the end of use; The liaison officers can send a quote.	Registration is free of charge, open to all and gives access to various GESIS services and data. Some services (e.g. data archiving) have a fee for use, directly displayed on their webpages.	Free and open access to data and products. Data Centre will facilitate data re-use by providing free and open access to data	All data offered open and for free	Data available freely, meaning at no more than the cost of reproduction and delivery, without charge for the data itself
Application Requirement & Review Process	Required for physical/remote competitive access; SAMU handles peer-review process	Submission form to access the services, with scientific evaluation and confirmation of the technical feasibility by the facility owner. The Central Hub manages	Application for VREs via Gateways	Required for research use; ECMWF evaluates scope and compliance	Applications for sponsored, paid, or partnership access; aligned to project requirements	–	Application and review for compliance, feasibility, and ethics by local access officers; Applications for physical or remote access to services follow an established review process based on compliance with EMBRC's mission and ethics policy	–	No application for public data; restricted levels require registration	No application for public data; tracking through registration	Application required for restricted datasets; handled by data centres

		project review.										
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2.3 Overview summary

2.3.1 RI's Data Policies overview

The comparison of data policies from RIs participating in IRISCC (Table 2) highlights common practices and notable differences across key topics.

Most RIs address policies to researchers and institutions, with some (e.g. ECMWF, ICOS) including policymakers and public users. The scope consistently covers research data, but some RIs (e.g., EMBRC, SeaDataNet) also include commercial users.

All RIs promote open access aligned with FAIR principles, though some impose conditions for downloading datasets, such as registration (e.g. IAGOS) and acceptance of licence.

Most RIs use Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) licences for open data, but exceptions exist to limit the use of data to non-commercial purposes (e.g., ECMWF).

Quality control responsibilities vary across the RIs landscape, with options for using central facilities (e.g., ICOS), while other RIs place responsibility on data producers (e.g. ANAEE).

IPRs are typically retained by data originators, though some RIs (e.g. ANAEE, ICOS) claim ownership of outputs generated within their facilities.

All RIs require citation, but acknowledgment practices vary from formal templates (e.g., EMBRC, IAGOS) to citation buttons directly displayed in the service catalogues (e.g., GESIS). Embargo periods are permitted for sensitive data, with durations defined by agreements.

In terms of legal compliance, all RIs align with EU frameworks such as GDPR, INSPIRE, and OECD guidelines, but some also follow sector-specific regulations (e.g. ECMWF acknowledges the WMO Resolution 40 for meteorological data).

Usage tracking methods differ, with some (e.g., ICOS) using their data portals, while others (e.g., ANAEE) employ KPIs. Commercial use requires separate agreements in most cases and is sometimes excluded from free access (e.g. ECMWF).

Most RIs offer dedicated online helpdesks, FAQs, or service portals with documentation, but the level of detail and support varies from detailed guides and user manuals to generic contact forms.

Overall, the policies demonstrate broad alignment on FAIR principles and legal compliance but differ in licensing conditions, IP ownership, and support mechanisms.

2.3.2 RI's Service provision overview

The comparison of service provisions from RIs participating in IRISCC (Table 3) highlights common approaches and distinct practices.

All RIs provide datasets and analytical tools as services, with RIs offering specialised services such as experimental platforms (e.g., ANAEE), forecasting tools (e.g., ECMWF), and on-site access to research facilities (e.g., EMBRC, eLTER).

A common practice among RIs is the use of dedicated service catalogues and data portals, with web Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) common for digital access. Another practice, such as for SeaDataNet, is to rely on federated services. Some RIs (e.g., eLTER) are in the process of developing their platforms.

Registration for service access is commonly required, often with the option for institutional login or ORCID integration (e.g., ICOS, GESIS). Affiliation with a recognised institution is sometimes needed for accessing specific services (e.g., ECMWF, EGI). Other restricted accesses may include peer-reviewed selection for access (e.g., ACTRIS, ANAEE). Access can also be restricted in case of sensitive data or limited-service capacity (e.g., ICOS), provided based on demonstration of scientific excellence in such cases.

SLAs and data use agreements are in some cases used to manage services provision, access and use across the RIs and their partners. Those agreements may define the fees to access services for RIs that charge for certain access types (e.g., ACTRIS and ECMWF), although free services or cost-recovery based service provision (e.g., ICOS, SeaDataNet) is more common practice.

In case of competitive access policy to services, formal peer reviewed applications are required (e.g., ACTRIS, ANAEE, ECMWF), but in other cases open-access models allow immediate access to public datasets (e.g., SeaDataNet, GESIS).

Overall, common trends among RIs include the use of open-access models, web-based service catalogues, and FAIR principles. Differences emerge around user eligibility, access controls, pricing policies, and review processes, reflecting the diverse missions and user bases of participating RIs.

3 Recommendations for data policy and procedures for digital service provided via IRISCC

3.1 Foreword

The IRISCC policy for data and digital service provision should aim at setting the principles to govern the collection, storage, management and efficiency of provided data and services. A common goal taken up in the harmonised data policies should be the optimal compliance with the FAIR principles of the RI data management system. It should ensure the FAIR principles. The data policy should also guarantee that data and services are run and managed ethically.

The recommendations provided in this section have been formulated from the analysis of best practices from established RIs presented in Table 2 and Table 3.

They aim at supporting harmonisation across the data and services made available from existing RIs or developed in collaboration with them in the frame of the IRISCC mission. The list of recommendations is made as exhaustive as possible, with certain recommendations that may be used only in specific cases and potentially left over for more generic cases. In general, the reviewed documentation and practices from RIs promote the principles of FAIR and Open science for harmonising data access and services implementations, to make data and services accessible, while also ensuring compliance with national and European legislation. The harmonisation also includes alignment of legal standards (licensing, intellectual property rights and data protection) as an underlying framework for sharing data and research.

The harmonising of strategies facilitates the integration of knowledge and services that in turn support efficient collaboration, and as a result, better understanding of climate change and assessment of risks.

3.2 Key recommendations for data policy

3.2.1 General content

- **Title & Dates:** Provide an appropriate title that makes clear whose policy it is and what the policy relates to and provide validity period including creation and implementation dates.
- **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs):** Assign PIDs (e.g., DOIs) to policy versions for traceability.
- **Scope of the policy:** Define coverage (e.g., data, software, services) and define and make publicly available the terms on access, IPR, privacy, and usage constraints.
- **Definitions:** Provide clear definitions of the technical and legal terms where required, including 'data' and 'services'.
- **Alignment with FAIR and Open-Access Principles:**
 - Make explicit reference to and align with the practical requirements relating to FAIR principles.
 - Link data outputs to specific researchers using researcher identifiers, to support the overall FAIRness.
 - Register the policy in open access registry services (e.g., FAIRsharing) and ensure it is consistently described and both human and machine readable.
- **Ethical aspects:** Emphasise ethical data use with a "user code of conduct", supporting users to comply with the policy requirements, ensuring responsible research practices.
- **Reference to standards and open-source tools:** Encourage the use of generic, domain and/or community standards or protocols wherever possible. Encourage open-source software and tools for data processing and modelling to support community collaboration.
- **Community Endorsement:** Ensure that the policy is endorsed by the community of users of the RI.
- **Compliance:** Users should be required to comply with the RI's data policy and national and European legislation.
- **Policy review:** Establish procedures for reviewing and updating policies to adapt to evolving legal, technical, security and organisational changes.

3.2.2 Legal and community standards framework

The data policy and procedures for provision of digital services must comply with the overall European Union and national legal frameworks, and international principles, related to the relevant (environmental) data, information and databases, health and safety at work and align with relevant directives and guidelines. A non-exhaustive list of references that should be acknowledged and complied with is provided in Annex 1.

- **Standards:** Use established international standards and data formats recognised by international institutions and relevant for the types of activities considered (e.g., INSPIRE, ISO, OGC, NetCDF, JSON).
- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):**
 - **Data Privacy:** Personal and sensitive data must be handled in compliance with ethical considerations and with the EU GDPR. Define the level, content, the storage conditions and retention period of the data collected. Typically, personal data should be retained for the duration of the project.
 - **Access to personal information:** Users must have the right to access their personal information, and to have this information corrected and amended.
 - **Personal information collection:** Personal information may be collected using online forms, the data of which should be stored on secured repositories, accessible only to the relevant persons (e.g., RI's TA and dissemination coordinators). Explicit consent from the concerned users is required for any stored personal information. Personal information related to data contributions shall be stored together with the metadata on the contributed data to allow for proper citation and acknowledgement of the data.
 - Repositories for personal data may be a home repository and both the form, and the repository should comply with SSL technology and adheres to GDPR.

3.2.3 Open access and access restrictions

- **Availability Statement:** Clearly state how to access services and data, or how to request legitimate access.
- Structure the data policy around, and promote, the FAIR and Open Science principles [R8]. Ensure that data and digital services are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable by making them discoverable and easily accessible:
 - Findability: Ensure that data are assigned unique and PIDs and that data and services are properly catalogued with metadata standards to facilitate searchability.

- Accessibility: Data and services should be easily accessible through well-defined protocols, ensuring that users can download and use them without unnecessary barriers.
- Interoperability: Encourage the use of widely accepted common formats and standards to ensure data and services can be combined and used across various platforms.
- Reusability: Clear licensing and quality metadata are key to ensure that data and services can be used and reused.
- The F-UJI tool can be used to test the FAIRness of the used PIDs: <https://www.f-uji.net/>
- **Data types:** Regarding access rights and restrictions, data may be classified as follows:
 - Open / Non sensitive: Data freely available/accessible to User(s) either for download or for direct use within the RI.
 - Restricted / Sensitive: Data that are available under defined conditions. Restrictions may mean that fees could be charged. While metadata shall always be available at no charge, fees, if any, should be no higher than the actual cost of making the data available.
 - Embargoed: Data that are available only after an embargo period that cannot exceed a defined amount of time (e.g. 3 years maximum). Once the embargo period has passed, data should become Open.
- **Data sharing:** The policy should clearly state that data sharing is allowed, unless there are valid reasons not to share the data, and in such case provide clarity on legitimate exceptions to data sharing.
- **Limitations and restrictions:** Reasonable limitations and restrictions, still in line with the principle of open access, may be applied when data or service access could compromise a potential industrial or commercial use, lead to a breach in personal data protection or confidentiality rules, or when the access could affect a human subject or the protection of endangered species, or for reasons of national security.
- **Non-respect of the policy:** Measures in case of non-respect of the policy should be considered e.g., denial of future access to datasets and services.

3.2.4 Metadata and documentation

- **Metadata Schema:** Develop a metadata schema to ensure data management and facilitate reuse. The schema should provide structural and contextual information about datasets, including research project details such as experimental context, users, analysis methods, and logistical information. Guidelines for designing Metadata are available on the website of the [European Union](#) or on websites of institutions (e.g. [University of Louvain](#)).

- **Metadata Sharing:** The policy must mandate open access to metadata, with a CC0 licence, and clearly state access conditions within metadata records.
- **Open access:** Metadata should always be free and available at any time, even for restricted and embargoed data.

3.2.5 Licencing and Intellectual Property Rights

The data policy should provide clear definitions of ownership and licensing.

- **Licences:**
 - Use licences that provide legal clarity about open access, use, sharing, and exploitation of RI data and services, and give explicit permission to use work created by the owner.
 - Adhere to clear licensing policies, such as the **Creative Commons** licensing framework, to indicate how data and services can be used and reused by others.
 - Preferably use the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence, Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication or equivalent.
 - A well recommended licence is Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0), which lets others distribute, remix, adapt, if credits to the original creation are properly attributed.
 - For sensitive material, more restrictive licences such as CC-BY-NC-ND (non-commercial, no derivatives), may be applied for a controlled-access model of proprietary or confidential information.
- **Licences for software:** Use open licences such as, **MIT Licence**, **Apache License 2.0**, or **GNU General Public License v3**
- **Use open sources for the backend code of digital services**, combined with Creative Commons Licences (for data and documentation).
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR):**
 - **Ownership & IPR:** Ownership and intellectual property rights to data, services, databases, software, prototypes, new tools or methodologies or any other generated products should be defined as belonging to those who have generated them.
 - **Joint ownership:** In case when a proposal requests scientific collaboration with a service, or access, provider during activities within the RI, then the ownership should be shared by the user and the provider. In such a case a joint ownership agreement may be signed before the access starts.
 - **IPR for Commercial use:** IPR regarding data and services used for commercial interests must be clearly defined and IPRs respected.
 - **Third party rights:** Third party rights are IPRs that RIs have not generated themselves and do not own. In cases where RIs use such third-party rights as part of their own intellectual property, they must ensure that the IPRs of

the third parties are respected and that they have the authorisation of the right holders to grant access rights in accordance with this policy.

3.2.6 Citations and publications

- **Citation:**
 - Define clear guidelines for citation to credit data and services owners, using standardised citation practices.
 - Citation should include the use of PIDs and versioning to track modifications.
 - Related guidance may be provided to advise on how to cite a broader range of research outputs including software, actors and enablers such as data and services managers, funding bodies, research infrastructures and organisations.
- **Publications:**
 - Users are expected to make their publications available through open access repositories aligned with FAIR principles for storage, providing guidance on suggested repositories that may be used.
 - Users of IRISCC services, either accessed remotely or via TA or VA, must appropriately acknowledge the use of these services, authorship and intellectual property, in any resulting publications, patents, data products, or other outputs, following standardised citation formats and detailed guidance.
 - For each service, standardised citation formats and detailed guidance should be made available via the IRISCC website or service catalogue.
 - Acknowledgment statements could follow the formats suggested below:
 - *Acknowledging IRISCC:* The production of this work/product has been enabled by IRISCC <website>
 - *Acknowledging the use of Virtual Research Environment:* The production of this work/product has been enabled by the <VRE name> working environment (<VRE URL>) via the <gateway name> (<gateway URL>) operated by IRISCC.
 - *Acknowledging the use of VA:* The production of this work/product has been enabled via Virtual Access to <name of partner/institute/database providing the data> and IRISCC Virtual Access under EU-H2020 Grant Agreement No.X <XXX>.
 - *Acknowledging the use of TA:* The production of this work/product has been enabled via Transnational Access to <name of partner/station/database providing the data> and IRISCC Transnational Access under EU-H2020 Grant Agreement No. <XXXX>.
 - *Acknowledging the use of services:* The production of this work/product has been enabled by means of the <name of the

service> service offered via the <gateway name> (<gateway URL>) operated by IRISCC.

- *Acknowledging the use of Dataset / any research object:* The production of this work/product has been enabled by dataset(s) retrieved from the <gateway name> (<gateway URL>) operated by IRISCC.
 - Acknowledge in publications the support of the European Commission's H2020 Framework Programme under the appropriate grant agreement, the support of the program and the host institute.
- **Authorship** or contributor credit should be offered to IRISCC-affiliated scientists or technical staff who have made a substantive intellectual or scientific contribution to the work.
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** for new results (e.g., publications, patents, derived datasets) remain with the user, unless otherwise agreed. However, IRISCC retains rights to be informed of such outputs and may request copies for reporting or dissemination purposes.

3.3 Key recommendations for Digital service provision

3.3.1 Access to data and services

- **Cataloguing:** Maintain a service catalogue to help users navigate available digital services, including guidelines for users to easily find available services and datasets.
- **Web portals and dashboards:** Provide user-friendly web interfaces for easy access to services and data. Design intuitive portals, allowing users to search, visualise, and download data without technical expertise.
- **Access Management:** Implement authentication mechanisms (e.g., AAI) and federated identity systems enabling users to securely access data and services with a single sign-on.
- **Tiered access levels:** Consider defining user's profiles (e.g., academic, commercial, or governmental) with different levels of accessibility to the data and services, varying in restrictions for specific user groups, depending, for example, of the sensitivity of the data and services.
- **User's profiles:** The tiered access model may include user's profile who may be classified according to access rights and restrictions:
 - Anonymous Users: Access without any identification or accreditation.

- Registered: Identified access requiring prior registration.
- Authorised: Identified and authenticated access requiring specific permissions. Only a registered user can become an authorised user.
- **Transnational Access (TA):** Transnational access cannot be granted to an infrastructure/installation that is located in the same country where the user works.
- **Access monitoring:** Logs of data and services access, modifications, and sharing activities should be maintained for an appropriate period.
- **Set up the basis of a peer-reviewed process for user selection:** Describe the processes for application submission, for review of eligibility and scientific credibility, for establishment of selection panels and for communication of the results to the users.

3.3.2 Collaborative service provision

- **User needs assessment:** Consult users to tailor services according to their needs, by gathering feedback from researchers and stakeholders to design an intuitive digital platform that meets scientific and operational requirements.
- **Services Interoperability:** Align services with established standards (e.g., OGC, INSPIRE) to facilitate interoperability across platforms, systems and datasets.
- **Collaboration Platforms:** Provide digital environments for collaborative activities, integrating data and services sharing tools that support multi-user projects and data integration across disciplines.
- **Customisable workflows:** Provide tailored data analysis services where users can create or use pre-defined workflows, for example offer virtual research environments (VREs) that allow users to run complex analyses using a combination of built-in and custom tools.
- **Federated services:** Promote a federated model of services, where multiple partners contribute to service provision, making services more scalable and sustainable.
- **Service Quality control:** Implement a quality control process to ensure the reliability and integrity of provided digital services, including automated validation checks and manual reviews. The service providers and the management team may be in charge of managing the quality of the provided services.

3.3.3 Data and services interoperability

- **Application Programming Interface (API):**
 - Provide an API to allow for seamless integration of data and services into external systems.

- Provide API-based access to data and services to allow users to integrate with the RI without manually downloading large datasets.
- **Federated search tools:** Use federated search tools to allow users to query and access distributed datasets and services across different nodes, in which data from various sources is made searchable through common interfaces.
- **Align with EOSC:** Align policies and protocols with EOSC to open the possibility for integration of data and services with EOSC, to promote pan-European data sharing and access, and to provide a unified platform for digital services and data.

3.3.4 Data and services security and protection

- **Security:** Facilities within IRISCC should implement security measures, backups, and disaster recovery plans tailored to institutional needs. The precise mechanism by which this is achieved can vary from service to service and may be left to the discretion of individual institutions. Regular testing and updates are required to ensure data resilience. Service providers must establish continuity plans, and facilities are encouraged to maintain independent backup strategies. Such strategies may follow recommendations regarding security provided by the government of the country in which the facility is located.
- **Data Management Plan:** The European Commission asks researchers to ensure that data generated in EU funded projects are handled with a DMP. The policy should require the development of a DMP, making clear at what stage the DMP will be prepared and that it will be updated over the life of the RI. Updated DMPs should be clearly versioned.
- **Issue reporting:** Provide mechanisms for reporting service and/or data misuse, or security breaches, to relevant authorities or stakeholders.
- **Users notification:** Include guidelines for scheduled maintenance windows and emergency downtime, notifying users in advance.
- **Backups:** Implement regular backups with redundant storage systems to safeguard data loss and service outages due to system failures.
- **Long-term sustainability:** Emphasise long-term strategies and define sustainable funding models and governance to guarantee long-term data preservation and maintain high-quality digital services over time and ensure their long-term viability.

3.3.5 Agreements

- For paid services: Define SLAs that ensure a high level of service availability for the digital services and continuous access to data.

- The SLA may specify the terms of access, uptime guarantees, data storage, and user support services. SLAs can also define performance metrics, availability guarantees, and user responsibilities.
- The SLA may include regular monitoring and reporting on service performance, to ensure reliability, uptime, and performance metrics for digital services.
- For free services: Declare in the terms of use that no responsibility is taken for errors, mistakes or service interruptions.

3.3.6 Fees

- Clearly state the cost to access data and services where relevant.
- Researchers should be granted access to data and services for free whenever possible.
- Access to data should be provided free of charge to everyone.
- Access costs to the services should be declared based on actual costs.

3.3.7 User support

- **Support and documentation:** Provide comprehensive user manuals, tutorials, and helpdesks supporting users via documentation, FAQs, and interactive support mechanisms like webinars, workshops, help desks, and community forums.
- **Helpdesk and Support Services:** Offer user support through a helpdesk or dedicated support team to guide users through, application, access process and using of datasets and digital services.
- **User Feedback Mechanisms:** Issue surveys to collect user feedback and data on user satisfaction.

4 Conclusions and way forward for implementation

A harmonised connection and integration between IRISCC and service providers are key to the interoperability of data and services made available via IRISCC.

The current landscape of RIs participating in IRISCC is a fragmented network of heterogeneous proprietary systems reflecting specific needs, policies and procedures of individual institutions. Multiple policies and protocols for providing services within the landscape of RIs participating in IRISCC could hinder the successful delivery of IRISCC services.

In some cases, such as for FAIR and open-access principles, intellectual property rights, management of personal data, etc., policy areas are covered by national or European legislation, providing for a base level of harmonisation across all institutions. However, there are variations in some aspects of the reviewed data policies (e.g., licensing, quality control responsibilities, citation methods) and in the practical implementation of the provision of services (see section 2.3).

By identifying data policy and best practices across partner RIs, there is potential to consolidate and harmonise the services proposed by IRISCC. Harmonisation shall thus simplify development and implementation of IRISCC services across participating institutions.

The recommendations provided in section 3 have been designed to strengthen common purpose within the landscape of RIs participating in IRISCC by adopting a common framework for policy harmonisation and capacity enhancement across multi-disciplinary service providers. Among the multiple aspects of data policies and procedures for service provision reviewed for this report, the application of the FAIR principles to data, data and services interoperability and standardisation appear as essential factors for harmonisation and as critical aspects in multi-disciplinary research programs. Other fundamental aspects of the recommendations include to harmonise access to data and services, with recommendations for access to fit with the needs of multiple profiles of users.

As a way forward, the recommendations need to be implemented to develop a common policy framework across the distributed network of IRISCC. We have provided in Annex 2 a template for a Data and Services Policy for IRISCC, that can now be filled using the provided recommendations that are the most appropriate for IRISCC purposes. Such a task requires discussions and agreements with the service providers, which may be handled by the IRISCC RI Board.

5 References

Reference	
No	Description/Link
R1	European Research Infrastructures – European Commission , visited 04/04/2025
R2	Research Infrastructures – European Commission , visited 04/04/2025
R3	Ródenas, M., & Muñoz, A. (2023). ATMO-ACCESS MS1.2 Analysis of Access policies and legal framework regulating the Access provision (Version 1). CEAM. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13355072
R4	Davidson, J., Grootveld, M., Verburg, M., van Horik, R., O'Connor, R., Engelhardt, C., Garbuglia, F., Vieira, A., Newbold, E., Proudman, V., & Horton, L. (2022). FAIR-enabling Data Policy Checklist (1.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6225775
R5	Asmi, A., Jeffery, K., & Glaves, H. M. (2023). ENVRI-FAIR D4.6: Draft policy document for common service catalogue (1.1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10362930
R6	Jeffery, K., Glaves, H. M., & Best, M. (2023). ENVRI-FAIR D4.7: Policies for common service catalogue, policy landscape in EOSC domain (Version 1). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8119388
R7	European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures – Principles and guidelines for access and related services, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/8299402
R8	Wilkinson, M, Dumontier, M, Aalbersberg, I, et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific data, 3(1): 1–9. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex 1: References to legal framework and guiding principles

European legal framework:

- 1 Aarhus Convention (access to environmental data),
- 2 Directive 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019L1024>). Replacing Directive 2013/37/EU on the re-use of public sector information Text with EEA relevance, no longer valid.
- 3 Regulation (EU) 2021/694 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2021 establishing the Digital Europe Programme and repealing Decision (EU) 2015/2240.
- 4 EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 on the legal protection of data revealing personal details of individuals such as researchers and collectors (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679>).
- 5 Council Directive 89/391/EEC of 12 June 1989 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work,
- 6 Directive 2007/2/EC on establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community ([Eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/EC](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/EC)) and the INSPIRE principles ([Inspire.ec.europa.eu/principles](https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/principles)), regarding the sharing of spatial information among public sector organisations and access to the spatial data,
- 7 Directive 1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1483614313362&uri=CELEX:32014R1143>).
- 8 Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A01992L0043-20130701>).
- 9 Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases ([Eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/96/9/EC](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/96/9/EC)),
- 10 Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs ([Eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/2009/24/EC](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/2009/24/EC)),

- 11 Directive 2009/147/EC on the conservation of wild birds (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2009/147/oj>).

International Principles:

- 12 European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures [R7], principles and guidelines for access policies.
- 13 OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding.
- 14 The principles of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Declaration (<https://www.esfri.eu/latest-esfri-news/european-open-science-cloud-eosc-declaration>).
- 15 The Aarhus Convention (access to environmental data).
- 16 The FAIR principles

6.2 Annex 2: Template of data and service policy

Title:

Authors:

Grant number:

Date:

Version:

Document history (table):

Table of contents:

Executive Summary:

Keywords:

List of abbreviations:

FAIR – Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability

List of tables:

Table 1 – Caption (Page XX)

Acknowledgements:

1. General Introduction

- State what does the data and service policy govern within the Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks.
- Indicate that relevant definitions are listed in Annex.
- Provide definition and purpose of the RI:
- How are the data and services provided?
- Aim of the policy and link with other governance documents:
- Who does the policy apply to?
- Mention relevant tools / processes who helped design the policy, and the DMP.

2. Guiding principles

2.1. Open and FAIR data and services

- Promotion of open access, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), and open-source principles, with careful consideration of CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles if relevant.
- State that data have persistent identifiers (PIDs), and that data and services are discoverable, retrievable via standard protocols, and accessible to the greatest extent possible, with clear conditions for restricted data.

- State that metadata are always available, including for restricted or embargoed data.
- State that data and services are interoperable, machine-readable, and well-documented for effective reuse.
- State the cost for accessing data and services.

2.2. Ethical and legal compliance

- Adhere to European, international, national, institutional data regulations, and any relevant regulation, ensuring respect for privacy and ethical standards.
- State that in accordance with good scientific practice, users are encouraged to acknowledge the contribution of the Research Infrastructure in any output (i.e. publication, patent, data, etc.) deriving from research conducted within its realms, and to offer co-authorship to those working at the Research Infrastructure having made genuine scientific contributions to their work.

2.3. Sustainability

- State that publications shall follow open-access principles.
- State that data will be stored in certified data repositories to ensure long-term data preservation, security, and access, even in the case of decommissioning of the infrastructure.

2.4. Adaptive policy

- State how the policy will be evolving with technological advancements and emerging trends in data management.

3. European Legal Framework and International Principles

- Statement of full compliance with European Union and national legal frameworks. All users of the data, collections, and services must adhere to the legal and regulatory frameworks, and international principles, related to environmental data, information, databases, and personal data and privacy protection.
- Statement of integration of national laws, ensuring full legal compliance at the institutional and national levels.
- Reference to non-exhaustive list of references acknowledged and complied with by, to be provided in Annex.

4. Implementation of the FAIR Principles

Statement of FAIRness.

4.1. Findability

Persistent Identification

Describe measures in place for identifying the data.

Identification of people and organisations

Describe how the users will be identified.

4.2. Accessibility

Open access

- State a principle of open access data and services: "as open as possible, as closed as legally necessary".
- Define the level of openness of data and services and justify exceptions.
- Describe the open access implementation procedure.
- State that personal information and sensitive collection details are protected under GDPR and other relevant regulations.

Storage

- Define the principles and procedures for storage

Repository Systems

- Reference to relevant repositories.

4.3. Interoperability and Standardisation

Standardisation

- Statement on how data and services are standardised within IRISCC.

Interoperability

- Statement of how data and services are made interoperable within IRISCC.

4.4. Reusability

Data and services Quality

- Explain protocol for data and services validation and quality control. Make reference to the DMP.
- Define responsibilities for validation.

Licences

- Favour the use of open licences.
- Metadata should always be freely accessible, with licences like Creative Commons Zero (CC0) encouraged.
- Restrictions must be justified, temporary, and documented, with metadata remaining openly available.

Preservation and Archiving

- Process for ensuring long-term preservation of data and services to maintain readability, accessibility, and resilience against corruption or loss.

Security, backup and recovery

- Security protection measures implemented: backups, disaster recovery plans tailored to institutional needs.

- Service providers must establish continuity plans, and facilities are encouraged to maintain independent backup strategies.

5 Intellectual Property Rights

- Define who owns the data, services, databases, software, prototypes, new tools or methodologies or any other generated products
- They should be defined as belonging to those who have generated them.

6 Service provision

a. Access eligibility

Define who can access and criterium for access.

b. Types of access

Define the different types of access.

c. Access procedure

Define the process to access data and services.

d. Access monitoring and restrictions

Describe protocol for access monitoring and potential access restrictions.

e. Access suspension

Define cases and protocol and terms for access suspension.

7 Routes for dispute resolution

State that in case of a dispute IRISCC prioritises resolving issues amicably through dialogue among the involved parties. Should a dispute remain unresolved, a formal notification of dispute can be submitted by any involved party in writing to IRISCC central team, detailing the issue, evidence, and desired outcome, provided it has not already been brought before a competent court.

8 Acknowledgement and Citation

- Provide guidance for acknowledging IRISCC in publications or any output work or activity. Refer to the use of PIDs.

9 Policy management and Review

- Statement for the management and monitoring of the implementation of the data policy.
- Measures in case of violation of the policy: Violations of this data policy may result in sanctions, including suspension of access rights, revocation of data contributions, or legal action.

10 References

Wilkinson, M, Dumontier, M, Aalbersberg, I, et al. 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1): 1–9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

11 Annex 1 – Glossary

FAIR principles: Guiding principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (Wilkinson et al., 2016), which essentially means to make these data fit for autonomous processing by machines (Machine-Actionability. See <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

12 Annex 2 – References to Legal Framework and International Principles

European legal framework:

- Directive 96/9/EC on the legal protection of databases ([Eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/96/9/EC](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/96/9/EC)).

International Principles:

- The OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding (OECD, 2007), as recommended by the European Commission.